

A heterogeneous benchmark dataset for data analytics: Multiphase flow facility case study

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ABSTRACT

Improvements in sensing, connectivity and computing technologies mean that industrial processes now generate data from a variety of disparate sources. Data may take a number of forms, from time-domain signals, sampled at various rates using a variety of sensors, to alarm and event logs. Novel techniques need to be developed to tackle the challenges of heterogeneous data. Testing such algorithms requires benchmark datasets that allow direct comparison of the performance of the methods. This work presents the PRONTO heterogeneous benchmark dataset. Experiments were conducted on a multiphase flow facility under various operational conditions with and without induced faults. Data were collected from heterogeneous sources, including process measurements, alarm records, high frequency ultrasonic flow and pressure measurements. The presented dataset is suitable for developing and validating algorithms for fault detection and diagnosis and data fusion concepts. Three algorithms are tested using the dataset, illustrating the applicability of the dataset.

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1. Introduction

Industrial plants typically contain many potential sources of data, ranging from sensors used for control and monitoring of the process, to event logs or video records. Considering these multiple sources of heterogeneous data jointly offers a number of opportunities for improved reliability and robustness of monitoring algorithms. Novel techniques need to be developed to tackle the challenges of heterogeneous data.

Testing such algorithms requires benchmark datasets that allow direct comparison of the performance of the methods. The Tennessee Eastman process plant [1] is a widely used simulator for generating datasets for validating different control and monitoring methods. The wind turbine competition model [2] is another benchmark case which is widely used for comparing different fault

detection and diagnosis methods. A further benchmark case [3] provides a reference dataset for fault detection and identification in batch processes. These benchmarks do not have any experimental measurements or information from alarm or event logs, providing simulated data both from a healthy system and from a system with simulated fault conditions. In contrast to these case-studies based on simulated data, industrial-scale case studies like the multiphase flow benchmark case study in [4] or the carbon capture case study [5] do provide measurements recorded from a real world system. However these datasets are relatively homogeneous in nature, containing only standard process measurements. Therefore there is a need for a new benchmark study to support the development and validation of advanced process and condition monitoring techniques based on heterogeneous data.

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This work aims to fill this gap by describing the PRONTO² heterogeneous benchmark dataset based on an industrial-scale multiphase flow facility. It includes data from heterogeneous sources, including process measurements, alarm records, high frequency ultrasonic flow and pressure measurements, an operation log and video recordings. The study collected data from various operational conditions with and without induced faults to generate a multi-rate, multi-modal dataset. This work is an extension of a preliminary study, where the dataset was introduced along with the process description and experimental set-up [6]. This paper gives an extended description of this dataset and provides insights for the development of monitoring algorithms. The dataset is suitable for developing and validating algorithms for fault detection and diagnosis (FDD) and data fusion. Its suitability is established by means of three FDD algorithm examples tested on the dataset.

The PRONTO benchmark dataset described in this paper is available in the following repository: [7]. The repository contains both raw and pre-processed data files. A technical report [8] detailing the experiments and data is also stored in the repository.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the multiphase flow facility. Sections 3 and 4 introduce the types of data and give an overview of the operating conditions and the induced faults in the heterogeneous dataset. Section 5 shows observations from the dataset. Section 6 presents potential uses of the benchmark dataset for algorithm development, while Section 7 demonstrates how data fusion might be applied using the dataset. Section 8 presents three examples of how the benchmark dataset might be used for the development and validation of FDD algorithms. Section 9 discusses the challenges and future research directions in FDD, the paper ends with concluding remarks in Section 10.

2. The multiphase flow facility

The PRONTO benchmark dataset was collected from the industrial-scale, fully automated, high pressure, multiphase flow facility in the Process System Engineering Laboratory of Cranfield University. The facility allows multiphase flows comprised of water, air and oil to be studied. It was designed for the investigation of the transportation, measurement and control of multiphase flows. A different set-up of the facility has been previously used for investigating process monitoring approaches that only make use of process data [4].

Fig. 1 shows a schematic of the process. Water and air are mixed and then separated using a two-phase and a three-phase separator. The third phase (oil) was not used in the case study. The input air and water flows are mixed in the mixing zone. Various operating conditions can be investigated by adjusting the set points of flow controllers FIC302, FIC301, FIC102 and FIC101 in the SCADA system. The two-phase flow is directed through a horizontal pipeline to a 2" riser. The horizontal pipeline can be bypassed by manipulating the U39 manual valve (near the middle of Fig. 1), which allows the flow to be led straight to the riser. In the middle of the riser there is an S-shape section. At the top of the riser the two-phase separator separates the liquid and gas phases. Both the liquid and the gas phases are led into to the three-phase separator (at the lower left of Fig. 1). The water is returned to the storage tank and the

² PRONTO (PROcess NeTwork Optimization for efficient and sustainable operation of Europe's process industries taking machinery condition and process performance into account) is an Innovative Training Network European Industrial Doctorate project funded by the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions scheme under Horizon 2020. The PRONTO heterogeneous benchmark dataset is an output of the PRONTO multiphase flow benchmark case study, which is a deliverable of the H2020 PRONTO project.

Table 1
Heterogeneous data in the PRONTO benchmark dataset.

Data type	Sampling rate	Storage policy
Process measurements	1 Hz	Regularly sampled
Alarm, event, change logs	Event-driven	Discrete events
Ultrasonic flow measurements	10 kHz	60 s recordings
High frequency pressure measurements	5 kHz	60 s recordings
Videos	–	30–60 s recordings

Table 2
Process variables.

Tag	Description	Unit
FT305/302	Input air flow rate	Sm ³ h ⁻¹
FT305-T	Input air temperature	°C
PT312	Air delivery pressure	bar(g)
FT102/104	Input water flow rate	kg s ⁻¹
FT102-T	Input water temperature	°C
FT102-D	Input water density	kg m ⁻³
PT417	Pressure in the mixing zone	bar(g)
PT408	Pressure at the riser top	bar(g)
PT403	Pressure in the 2-phase separator	bar(g)
FT404	2-phase separator output air flow rate	m ³ h ⁻¹
FT406	2-phase separator output water flow rate	kg s ⁻¹
PT501	Pressure in the 3-phase separator	bar(g)
PIC501	Air outlet valve 3-phase separator	(%)
LI502	Water level 3-phase separator	(%)
LI503	Water coalescer level	(%)
LVC502	Water coalescer outlet valve	(%)
LI101	Water tank level	m

air flow is exhausted to the atmosphere through PIC501. The facility is instrumented with various pressure, flow rate, temperature and density sensors. Besides the standard process instrumentation, there are also sensors providing high frequency pressure and ultrasonic measurements. The high frequency pressure sensors are distributed along the pipelines from the mixing zone to the riser top while the ultrasonic flow sensor is located at the riser top. Two transparent pipe sections, located at the top and the bottom of the riser, allow the flow regime to be observed.

3. Heterogeneous data

Data were collected from heterogeneous sources, including process measurements, alarm records, high frequency ultrasonic flow and pressure measurements, an operation log and video recordings. The heterogeneity of the benchmark dataset is summarized in Table 1, where each data type is given alongside its associated sampling rate and storage policy. In the table, the term *storage policy* refers to the strategies employed for recording and storing the data. The data quality of the heterogeneous dataset is discussed later in Section 5.5.

3.1. Process measurements

Process variables were measured by the SCADA system, which is responsible for the control of the process and provides a means to retrieve measurements from all of the connected sensors at a regularly sampled 1 Hz sampling rate. Nineteen process variables are listed in Table 2 alongside their corresponding tags, location in the process and units. The technical report [8] provides a comprehensive list of process variables including the set points and controller outputs of flow controllers.

3.2. Alarms, events and changes logs

The SCADA system also recorded alarm, event and change logs at discrete events. Each log contained the time stamp, the corre-

Fig. 1. Schematic of the multiphase flow facility [6].

sponding sensor tag, the status and some additional information, such as area, process unit and parameters linked to the occurrence of alarm, event or change.

3.3. High frequency ultrasonic flow measurements

The instrument for the high frequency ultrasonic measurements was a non-invasive, clamp-on continuous wave Doppler ultrasound flow sensor with a 10 kHz sampling rate [9]. The capture of the ultrasound measurement was initiated intermittently to give a 60 s recording of the 10 kHz measurements for all tested scenarios described in Section 4. The sensor output is a voltage proportional to the Doppler frequency shift. The velocity of the flow can be calculated from the Doppler shift of the transmitted ultrasound using the conversion formula given in [10].

3.4. High frequency pressure measurements

High frequency pressure measurements were recorded at a 5 kHz sampling rate for 60 s for all of the tested scenarios described in Section 4. The locations of the nine pressure sensors are given in Fig. 1. The measurements are given in units of bar(g).

3.5. Operation log

The operating conditions, the data collection details, the valve openings for the induced faults and the times of changes were recorded in the operation log. The operation log complements the change logs recorded by the SCADA system allowing the exact operating sequences to be reconstructed.

3.6. Videos

The 2" pipeline has a transparent section at both the riser top and riser base. Videos were recorded for a period of 30–60 s during the tested scenarios to provide a better understanding of the flow regimes.

3.7. Pre-processed data

The benchmark dataset also includes pre-processed data files:

- The process measurements are labelled according to operating conditions and fault scenarios described in Section 4 using the operation log and videos.
- Each alarm log contains the timestamp, the corresponding sensor tag and status information, whether they are active or inactive. Based on this information they are transformed into a binary form aligned with the process measurements by rounding the time of the alarm event down to the nearest second as shown in [11]. The alarm logs are labelled similarly to the process measurements. The binary alarm value of alarm $A_{k,i}$ for sensor i and timestamp k can be formulated as follows:

$$A_k^i = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if no active } A^i \text{ for timestamp } k \text{ and no previous active } A^i, \\ & \text{or latest } A^i \text{ was inactive} \\ 1, & \text{if no active } A^i \text{ for timestamp } k \text{ and latest } A^i \text{ was active,} \\ & \text{or active } A^i \text{ for timestamp } k. \end{cases}$$

- The raw high frequency pressure measurements are converted to units of bar(g), by adding an offset and multiplying them with a constant value. The data repository contains the conversion parameters, while the technical report [8] provides a detailed description about the conversion.

Table 3
Tested operating conditions.

		Water flow rate (kg s ⁻¹)				
		0.1	0.5	1	2	3.5
Air flow rate (Sm ³ h ⁻¹)	20	Slugging	Slugging	Slugging	Slugging	Normal
	50	Slugging	Slugging	Slugging	Normal	Normal
	100	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal
	120	Normal	–	–	–	–
	150	–	Normal	–	–	–
	200	Normal	Normal	Normal	–	–

Table 4
Induced faults by valve openings.

Induced fault	Operating condition	Valve	Valve openings (°)
Air leakage	A	V10	0, 5, 10, 15
	B		0, 5, 10, 20, 15, 20, 25, 40, 90
Air blockage	A	V11	90, 80, 70, 60, 50, 40, 30, 20, 10
	B		90, 80, 70, 60, 50, 40, 30, 20, 10
Diverted flow	A	U39	5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60
	B		10, 20, 30, 40, 45, 50, 60

4. Faults and operating conditions

The PRONTO benchmark case study was conducted under 20 operating conditions implemented by adjusting the set points of air and water flow controllers in the SCADA system. Some of these operating conditions produced stable flow regimes, referred to as normal, while others produced unstable flow regimes, referred to as slugging. The air and water flow rate combinations are shown in Table 3. The high frequency measurements were recorded once the flow stabilized. Videos were recorded from the transparent section at the riser top. The SCADA system captured the process measurements and alarm logs during the start-up, shut-down and transition periods, but no high-frequency measurements were recorded during these periods.

4.1. Normal operating conditions

A representative normal training dataset is essential for developing monitoring algorithms. Thirteen operating conditions resulted in normal flow regimes, as shown in Table 3.

4.2. Slugging

Slugging is an unstable flow regime that occurs in multiphase risers when the gas and liquid flow rates are relatively low [12]. This phenomenon results in oscillations in the pressure, flow rate and density through the riser. Seven operating conditions induced slugging, as shown in Table 3.

4.3. Faults induced by manual valves

Three induced faults were manually introduced to the process to mimic process malfunctions. Table 4 summarizes the faults, which were induced by manually opening U39 and V11 or closing V10 (see valves in Fig. 1). For each of these faults two operating conditions were tested:

- Operating condition A: 120 Sm³ h⁻¹ air, 0.1 kg s⁻¹ water flow rates;
- Operating condition B: 150 Sm³ h⁻¹ air, 0.5 kg s⁻¹ water flow rates.

All tests started from normal operating conditions and the manual valves were gradually operated to induce the faults. The high

frequency measurements were taken once the flow stabilized at certain valve openings.

4.3.1. Air leakage

Air leakage was induced by gradually opening V10, which allowed the input air to leak out to the atmosphere instead of being led to the mixing zone. As the amount of input air was reduced, a cyclic behaviour was observed. This cyclic behaviour was characterized by periods of normal flow, followed by a period of no flow at the riser top, and subsequently followed by a flow of water with large air bubbles, before again returning to normal flow to restart the sequence. This behaviour was very similar to slugging, although the reason behind it was not only due to the reduced air flow rate but also due to the pressure reduction in the mixing zone caused by the leakage. Once all of the input air leaked out, the pressure dropped and only water remained in the mixing zone, leading to a liquid-only flow regime. Videos recorded at the transparent section at the riser top confirm the presence of this phenomenon.

4.3.2. Air blockage

Air blockage was induced by gradually closing V11, which reduced the amount of air supplied to the mixing zone. The flow regime for air blockage was different from the air leakage case as there was no pressure reduction or drop in the system. The flow remained continuous, although mild slugging was observed. There were no videos recorded for this fault.

4.3.3. Diverted flow

Mixed diverted flow was induced by gradually opening U39, which bypassed the horizontal pipeline and led the mixed flow directly to the riser. The diverted flow caused visible differences in the flow regime when compared to the normal flow at the transparent section of riser base, however there was no difference observed at the transparent section of the riser top. Videos were recorded from the transparent section at the riser base.

5. Observations from the dataset

Visual inspection can guide users of the benchmark dataset towards interesting aspects that they can use in their own work. In this section observations are given from various data types to show various process behaviours and data characteristics.

5.1. Observations from the process measurements

The characteristics and complexities of a processes, which should be the guideline for the design of data analytic algorithms, can often be inferred by visually inspecting the data. As an example, Fig. 2 shows a high density plot [13] of the normalized process measurements listed in Table 2 during normal and slugging condition. Several observations from this subset of data that may motivate the development of monitoring algorithms are discussed.

Observations from individual measurements: the measurement of a process variable is often contaminated by noise and errors due to measurement instruments. Fig. 3 shows the examples of process variables with quantization, compression and varying magnitudes of measurement noise. These issues should be addressed at the pre-processing stage.

Multivariate observations: correlations usually exist between process measurements that are physically close to or connected with each other in the process. A process measurement may also be autocorrelated with its historical values. Such relationships reflect the underlying nature of the process and faults may cause these relationships to change. Visualization of process measurements can indicate the relationships that may exist in the process, which can be traced back to the physical layout and operational history.

Fig. 2. Time trends of the process variables in normal and slugging conditions.

Fig. 3. Examples of noises and errors in process measurements.

Fig. 4(a) shows that the mixing zone pressure (PT417) and riser top pressure (PT408) are highly correlated, which can be explained by their proximate location and connection via pipelines in the facility. Fig. 4(b) shows the process variables related to the water storage tank T100. The derivative of water level in T100 (LI101) should be proportional to the difference between the inflow rate (proportional to the outlet valve opening of water coalescer LVC502) and the outflow rate (input water flow rate to the process FT102/104) according to the mass balance. This first-principles relationship can be used for data reconciliation in order to improve the measurement accuracy.

After changing the set points, transitions may occur before the process reaches the new steady state. Fig. 4(c) presents the step responses of the input air flow rate (FT302/305), input water flow rate (FT102/104), and the pressure in the input air line (PT312).

Oscillations in the measurements may exist due to the nature of the mechanical system, such as the physical vibration of the vertical riser, control effect, and unstable flow regimes, e.g. slugging in this case study. Fig. 4(d) shows a controlled variable (PT501) and the controller output associated with it (PIC501) with oscillations due

to the control effect. Such oscillations may trigger alarms during the transition between normal operating conditions.

5.2. Observations from the alarm logs

Only five alarm tags appeared in the dataset for the steady state observations. These alarms were transformed to binary alarm features to study their behaviour and occurrence as described in Section 3.7. The binary alarms for all of the manually induced faults for operating condition A are shown in Fig. 5. The technical report of the PRONTO benchmark dataset gives further analysis of alarms.

5.3. Observations from the high frequency ultrasonic flow measurements

Fig. 6 shows the raw ultrasonic flow measurement together with the flow velocities calculated from the raw measurements. It may be observed that even when only considering the raw measurements, the voltage amplitude is much more variable during slugging, than for the normal operating condition. In the first slugging condition (Fig. 6(a) and (b)), the flow rate fluctuates heavily

Fig. 4. Examples for multivariate observations.

Fig. 5. Alarms for operating condition A ($120 \text{ Sm}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ air, 0.1 kg s^{-1} water flow rates).

due to the severe slugs. However, in the case of the second slugging condition (Fig. 6(c) and (d)) and the third normal condition (Fig. 6(e) and (f)) the difference in the pattern is less radical. The second slugging condition has much shorter slugs, which the ultrasonic data is able to represent well, however these short slugs might not be picked up by the lower sampling rate of the process measurements.

5.4. Observations from the high frequency pressure measurements

There are no process measurements through the horizontal pipeline, the vertical riser and the S-shape section. However, the high frequency pressure measurements provide high resolution recordings of the pressure fluctuations at the horizontal pipeline and the riser, making them suitable for induced fault and flow regime detection. Fig. 7 shows measurements from the nine high frequency pressure sensors for a developing air leakage case. It can be observed that the signals exhibit large pressure oscillations when V10 is opened to 10° . However, once the air has leaked

out of the system (when V10 is opened to 15°) the pressure signals become stable due to the fact that only water remains in the pipeline.

Because of their locations, the high frequency pressure sensors provide correlated measurements. The correlation is dependent on the operating conditions and on the type of induced fault. Fig. 8 shows how the correlation varies for the leakage case of operating condition A ($120 \text{ Sm}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ air, 0.1 kg s^{-1} water flow rates) achieved by opening V10 gradually. In all cases the sensors on the S-shape section (P6, P7 and P8) are the most correlated due their proximity and the sensor on the top the riser (P9) is the least correlated with the rest. The correlation of the sensors at the first riser section (P4 and P5) changes the most during the introduction of the air leakage fault.

5.5. Data quality

Based on the observations in this section it can be stated that there are no missing data or corrupted measurements in the

Fig. 6. Ultrasonic flow measurements and calculated flow velocities.

Fig. 7. Pressure data for the air leakage case of operating condition A.

dataset. The two main sources of uncertainty are the measurement noise and the process disturbance. The measurement instrumentation may influence the data quality. For example, the process data contain quantized, compressed and noisy variables as shown in Fig. 3 due to the limitation of temperature, density, and pressure sensors.

The disturbance in process variables is caused by changes in operating conditions of the process [14]. For example the disturbance in the pressure measurements varies with the valve openings for the leakage case, as shown in Fig. 7. One may evaluate the data quality and identify the sources of uncertainty when using this dataset to develop and validate FDD algorithms so that the reliability and the robustness of these FDD algorithms can be improved.

6. Uses of the data for algorithm development

This section gives an overview of potential uses of the PRONTO benchmark dataset, based on Fig. 9, which shows a framework for fault detection and diagnosis (FDD). Examples are given of how the dataset could be used for testing pre-processing, feature design and FDD methods.

6.1. Pre-processing

Table 5 gives an overview of pre-processing steps with reference to the dataset.

– *Data preparation.* *Importing* refers to loading the raw data files to a processing environment, while *mapping* refers to matching the tag names in the raw data files with the notation in the process

Fig. 8. Correlation of the pressure sensors for the air leakage case of operating condition A.

Table 5
Pre-processing with reference to the benchmark dataset.

	Method	Relevant data
Data preparation	Map and import Synchronization	All data types Between high-frequency measurements and process measurements
Data exploration	Labelling Standard statistics Scatter plots High density plots	All data types
Data cleaning	Scaling Outlier detection	High-frequency pressure measurements N/A unless corrupted
Data verification	Filtering Missing data Data reconciliation	High-frequency measurements N/A unless corrupted Process measurements

diagram. Both steps are essential before analysis. The manually triggered high frequency measurements need to be *synchronized* with the process measurements. The dataset can be *labelled* with respect to health state and operating conditions using videos and the operation log.

- *Data exploration and visualization* includes calculating *standard statistics* (root mean squares, variance, higher order statistics),

and visualizing time domain plots, *scatter plots* and *high density plots*. The results (see Section 5) can help the user to gain insights for further development of data analytic approaches.

- *Data cleaning*. In the benchmark dataset, *scaling* is necessary so that the high frequency measurements are given in units of bar(g). *Outliers* are not a significant issue in this dataset. Signals may contain noise, which is any undesirable random or periodic component in a signal. The signal-to-noise ratio is a good indicator to inspect and compare the level of the measured signal to the level of background noise. The high-frequency measurements have been observed to be noisy, hence *filtering* methods might be necessary to remove the unwanted noise from the signals [15].
- *Data verification* examines the measurements and checks for consistency. There are no *missing data* in the benchmark dataset, however one might remove selected values to test missing data imputation methods. *Data reconciliation* can be adopted in order to reduce the influence of random error and improve the consistency in process measurements (e.g. the process data contains the inflow, outflow and the water level of the water storage tank in Fig. 1, which may be reconciled based on the mass balance).

6.2. Feature design

A *feature* is defined as an individual measured property of the monitored system [16]. When working with larger datasets with correlated and redundant variables, it is desirable to extract features which are representative, non-redundant and easily interpreted by experts. This step is called *feature extraction* and its methods vary by data type, sensor type and by monitoring pur-

Fig. 9. Typical structure of an FDD framework.

Table 6
Feature design in relevance to the benchmark dataset.

	Method	Relevant data
Feature extraction	Time domain Frequency domain Time-frequency domain	High-frequency measurements
Alarm features	Conversion to binary features Pattern matching	Alarm logs
Multivariate approaches	Linear methods Dynamic methods Kernel-based methods	Process measurements
Feature selection	Filters Wrappers Embedded methods	High-frequency measurements, process measurements

pose. Features may be further refined using *feature selection*. Table 6 shows which data within the PRONTO benchmark dataset are most suited to the development of new feature design methods.

– *Feature extraction*. Signal processing methods can be applied to high frequency data to extract *time domain*, *frequency domain* or *time-frequency domain* features. *Frequency-domain* analysis may be used to either quantify the properties of the whole spectrum or to extract features at certain frequencies or frequency bands from the signal. *Time-frequency* analysis investigates the signals in both the time and frequency domain [17]. Feature extraction methods are relevant to the high frequency measurements to gain valu-

able insight about the fault cases and operating conditions of the process [18].

- *Multivariate approaches*. Process variables may be correlated spatially and temporally due to the mass and energy transfer, the location of the sensors, and the control effect, which reflect the behaviour of the process. *Multivariate approaches* aim to extract time-series features in a less redundant feature space which are representative of the process behaviours [19]. *Linear methods*, such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA), can remove highly-correlated variables and obtain more representative features. For complexities in the process measurements such as those identified in Section 5.1, *kernel-based methods* and *dynamic methods* may be further developed to account for the non-linear relationship and the temporal correlation, respectively.
- *Alarm features*. Alarms are often stored in the form of historical logs which contain the name of the alarm, its status and level. The status of an alarm indicates whether or not a specific alarm is active or inactive [11]. Features can be extracted from alarms by transforming historical logs to binary or categorical variables by alarm name. Alarm feature extraction can also refer to the extraction of patterns in alarm floods [20].
- *Feature selection*. Features may be correlated and redundant. Feature selection aims to lower the correlation and redundancy of the features so that only the most relevant features are retained. *Filters* for feature selection rank the features using a relevance index without optimizing the performance of a predictor [21]. *Wrappers* take features as inputs, iterate through subsets of features with a learning algorithm and output an optimal subset based on the best predictive performance of the applied learning algorithm [16]. *Embedded methods* perform feature selection

Table 7
Fault detection and diagnosis.

	Method	Relevant data
Threshold-based methods	Pre-defined threshold Adaptive threshold Fuzzy threshold	Data and features from all types
Statistics-based methods	Monitoring statistics Contribution plots Causal map	Process measurements, time-series features
Model-based methods	First-principles models	N/A
Machine learning methods	Unsupervised learning Supervised learning	Unlabelled data and features Labelled data and features

while training and validating a learning algorithm, therefore they may be considered as similar to wrappers [21]. Feature selection methods can be applied to the features extracted from the high-frequency measurements or they can be an alternative to the multivariate approaches for the process measurements in the dataset.

6.3. Fault detection and diagnosis

FDD aims to achieve the early detection of faults, diagnosis of their root causes and their severities to avoid potential failures or shut-downs in the system [22]. Examples of FDD methods that can be tested and validated using this benchmark dataset are summarised in Table 7.

- *Threshold-based methods.* A threshold can be *pre-defined* based on expert knowledge, or adaptive to changing operating conditions. As a number of normal and slugging operating conditions were recorded in the benchmark dataset, these scenarios provide examples to test *adaptive* methods. The threshold may also be *fuzzy* [23]. A fuzzy method might report a mixture of faulty and normal operating conditions with associated probabilities. The gradually developing fault scenarios would be suitable for testing such a method.
- *Statistics-based methods.* The methods of statistical process monitoring use time-series features extracted by multivariate approaches for fault detection, identification, and reconstruction [24]. *Monitoring statistics*, such as the Hotelling's T^2 statistic and the squared prediction error (SPE), and their associated thresholds may be calculated for fault detection using the time-series features. When a fault is detected, *contribution plots* identify the influential process variables with respect to the fault occurrence [25]. Cause and effect relationships may exist between process measurements (e.g. the controller and mixing zone pressure PT417). It is possible to build a *causal map* of process variables by inspecting the physical layout of the process shown in Fig. 1. This can facilitate the diagnosis of the root cause of a fault and its propagation path in the process.
- *Model-based methods.* This dataset is not suitable for first-principles modelling because physical information about the plant, such as the volume of the separator and the lengths and friction factors of the pipes is not included in the dataset. However hybrid methods might be considered combining data-driven methods with model-based methods [26], where first-principles modelling is partially possible. For example, for the water storage tank T100 in Fig. 1, the model structure between its inflow (proportional to VC502), outflow (FT102/104) and water level (LI101) can be inferred based on the mass balance.

- *Machine learning methods.* *Unsupervised learning* methods, such as clustering analysis, may detect an anomaly, which can be a faulty or a new normal operating condition, using unlabelled raw data and unlabelled features. When the dataset and extracted features are labelled in the pre-processing stage *supervised* classification and regression methods can detect, diagnose and assess the severity of the faults in the dataset. In the benchmark dataset labelling can be conducted using the videos and the operation log.

6.4. Performance evaluation

The performance of a monitoring algorithm should be evaluated when it is applied to this benchmark dataset. As an example of performance evaluation, [27] compared the detection time, the number of false positive detections, and the number of missed detections of various FDD algorithms. For fault detection algorithms, the detection time is defined as the difference between the time when a fault is induced and the time when the algorithm detects this fault. For a dataset collected from healthy conditions, the false alarm (false positive detection in [27]) rate is defined as the percentage of samples being erroneously detected as faulty. For a dataset collected in faulty conditions, the missed alarm (missed detections in [27]) rate denotes the percentage of samples being erroneously detected as healthy. A monitoring algorithm is preferred if it can achieve a low false alarm rate, a low missed alarm rate and a short detection time for a developing fault such as the blockage fault in this dataset.

The accuracy of the diagnostic algorithms is measured by the ratio of correctly diagnosed samples to all of the tested samples. For a given operating condition, the correct classification rate denotes the ratio of samples which are correctly diagnosed relative to the total number of samples collected in this condition. The misclassification rate is the ratio of samples which are not correctly diagnosed to all samples. The performance is summarized in a confusion matrix which presents the correct classification rates and misclassification rates of all possible faulty conditions. A diagnostic algorithm is preferred when it has a high correct classification rate and a low misclassification rate.

7. Data fusion for FDD

Data fusion combines information from several sources in order to form a unified picture of the monitored system. Fusion takes place on the data-level, feature-level, or on the decision-level [28]. The multiphase flow facility is monitored with various sensors, with data being recorded and stored using multiple data acquisition systems. For such a heterogeneous dataset, feature-level or decision-level fusion methods have to be considered [29] to make appropriate use of each data source. In this section data fusion methods are discussed with reference to how the PRONTO benchmark dataset might be used in their development and validation.

7.1. Feature-level fusion

Feature-level fusion, as shown in Fig. 10(a) gives the freedom to use various features for each data source, however the features should be synchronized in time. The benchmark dataset is heterogeneous and is suitable for the validation of feature-level fusion methods combining features extracted from the high frequency measurements with the process measurements.

7.2. Decision-level fusion

Decision-level fusion combines monitoring results from various monitoring systems into one final monitoring result, as shown in

Fig. 10. Levels of data fusion.

Fig. 10(b). The inputs can originate from monitoring systems using various data types [30] as listed in Table 3, from monitoring systems focused on different parts of the system [31] or from monitoring systems using the same data type with different algorithms [32]. Decision-level fusion is well-suited for heterogeneous data because the different monitoring systems do not have to be sampling data at the same rate, do not have to be in the same format, and do not have to be embedded into the same type of individual monitoring system [11]. By exploiting the strengths and mitigating the weaknesses of each data type, the final monitoring performance can be improved compared to the individual monitoring systems. This heterogeneous dataset provides a good opportunity to validate decision-level fusion methods combining the monitoring results of monitoring systems developed for the different data types.

8. Demonstration of fault detection and diagnosis method on the benchmark dataset

This section gives demonstration examples regarding how this benchmark dataset can be used for FDD algorithm development. For the process data, PCA-enhanced Canonical Variate Analysis (CVA) [33] is applied as an example of a multivariate statistical approach for feature extraction. T^2 and SPE provide the monitoring statistics for fault detection, and the contribution plots provide fault diagnosis. Section 8.2 demonstrates a Bayesian method [6] to show how the high-frequency pressure data can be used for fault diagnosis, applying a frequency domain feature extraction method with a data-driven naive Bayes classifier. The last example, a two-stage Bayesian classifier, demonstrates how the process and alarm data can be used together for fault diagnosis by applying data-driven decision-level fusion [11]. The performance is evaluated according to the metrics proposed in Section 6.4.

8.1. Multivariate statistical process monitoring: PCA-enhanced CVA and contribution plots

8.1.1. Using PCA-enhanced CVA for monitoring

Due to the dynamic behaviour in the process measurements observed in Section 5.1, PCA-enhanced Canonical Variate Analysis (CVA) is selected as a candidate to demonstrate the feasibility of this case study in validating data-driven process monitoring algorithms. In PCA-enhanced CVA, PCA extracts principal components from the process measurements while CVA finds the linear combinations of these principal components which have maximum temporal correlations, making it suitable for addressing the dynamic behaviour. These linear combinations are taken as the features in the multivariate statistical process monitoring. The indicators of systematic and random errors, i.e. monitoring statistics T^2 and SPE, are calculated using the features obtained by PCA-enhanced CVA.

The process data from normal operating conditions A and B (described in Section 4.3) and the process data from the faulty scenarios with the air blockage, the air leakage and the diverted flow in

Table 8
Monitoring performance of PCA-enhanced CVA.

	Operating condition A			Operating condition B		
FA (%)	8.8			4.29		
DT (s)	Leakage	Blockage	Diverted	Leakage	Blockage	Diverted
	624	1498	1166	414	2332	344

both operating conditions are used for training the monitoring algorithm and testing its performance in fault detection and diagnosis. Due to the compression and quantization issues, the temperature and density measurements (FT305-T, FT102-T and FT102-D) are removed. The other 14 variables in Table 2 are used. The valve opening sequence for inducing the air blockage fault is plotted in Fig. 11.

8.1.2. Performance evaluation for fault detection

Table 8 presents the False Alarm (FA) rates of the healthy condition data and the detection time (DT) of the three faults obtained by PCA-enhanced CVA. For operating condition A, the data from healthy operation with no induced faults are divided into training and cross-validation sets. The monitoring model is trained on the training set and the FA rate is calculated on the cross-validation set. The FA rate for operating condition B is obtained in the same way.

For fault detection in operating condition A, the T^2 and SPE values of the faulty data sets, which are collected with manually induced faults, are calculated and compared with their control limits using the monitoring model trained for the same operating condition. A fault is defined to be detected once at least one of the monitoring statistics exceeds its control limit for more than 20 samples. This is because occasional spurious detections are expected even during normal operation due to measurement noise. Meanwhile the induced fault exists persistently and, as a result, the detection is also expected to persist. The DT is defined as the time difference between inducing the fault and detecting the fault. DTs for operating condition B is obtained in the same way.

Fig. 12 visualizes the T^2 and SPE for the air blockage fault in operating condition B. The detection occurs when the valve opening was switched from 40° to 30°. Occasional spurious detections exist before the detection when the monitoring statistics violate their thresholds. However, these violations are transient, whereas the monitoring statistic stays above the threshold after point X in Fig. 12.

8.1.3. Fault diagnosis using contribution plots

Fig. 13 shows the accumulated contributions of process variables to the monitoring statistics, which are the summations of their contributions during the period when the fault is detected. Such contribution plots facilitate fault diagnosis by highlighting the variables with large contributions to the monitoring statistics.

Fig. 11. Valve opening sequence, operating condition B with air blockage.

Fig. 12. Monitoring statistics obtained by PCA-enhanced CVA. Solid curves: monitoring statistics for the test set. Dashed lines: control limits of T^2 and SPE. X: fault detection.

Fig. 13. Accumulated contribution plots after fault detection.

It can be observed that Variable 2 (PT312), the inlet air pressure, and Variable 10, the air outlet valve opening of the three-phase separator (PIC501), have the largest contribution during the period when the fault is detected. Whilst the blockage fault will reduce the amount of air input, the pressure of the facility will be maintained by PIC501 and the entire facility will keep pressurized due to the feed-back control loop. To achieve this, PIC501 will close gradually as the amount of input air reduces. Therefore, when the blockage occurs, only the delivery pressure and the amount of air output, reflected by the valve opening of PIC501, will be influenced. These variables contribute the most to the monitoring statistics.

The results show that the PCA-enhanced CVA is responsive to fault occurrence and that the contribution plots can identify the process variables that are related to the fault. These results also show that this benchmark dataset is suitable for testing multivariate statistical process monitoring algorithms because the faults are well documented. The operating sequences for inducing faults can

provide the severity information about the fault when the monitoring algorithm detects this fault. For fault diagnosis, since the causes of faults are known, it is possible to verify that the contribution plots are highlighting the right process variables that are relevant to the fault.

8.2. A Bayesian method for fault detection and diagnosis

The high frequency pressure sensors are located on the horizontal and vertical riser and are located close to the valves which were used to manually induce the faults. Frequency domain features were extracted from the nine pressure sensor measurements. Each 60 s recording was divided into one second windows with no overlap, for which the frequency spectrum was calculated. The maximum amplitude of the spectrum from each 100 Hz frequency band was used as a feature, resulting in 25 features per second per pressure sensor. The features were normalized using the standard

Table 9
Confusion matrix of the Bayesian fault classification results.

	Diagnosed condition (%)	Diagnosed condition				
		Normal	Blockage	Leakage	Diverted	Slugging
Actual condition	Normal	82.93	9.5	1.34	0.03	6.21
	Blockage	19.05	75.56	0.42	0.02	4.94
	Leakage	24.15	5.00	64.88	3.41	2.55
	Diverted	0.59	0.20	2.53	96.08	0.60
	Slugging	32.25	1.90	3.66	0.19	62.00

Table 10
Diagnosis accuracies for two operating conditions.

Accuracy	Operating condition (%)	Operating condition	
		A	B
Alarm data		57.55	50.64
Process data		78.25	83.77
Fused data		83.95	90.16

score and labelled as normal, leakage, blockage, diverted flow and slugging classes accordingly.

The algorithm used for fault diagnosis is a single stage naive Bayes classifier, which calculates the likelihood of an observation belonging to a class, based on the Bayes theorem [30]. The feature set was randomly split into 70% training set and 30% test set for each fault case without using an additional validation set. Thresholds were set based on expert knowledge at the upper and lower 1% of the normal operation range. The results in Table 9 show the confusion matrix of the final results. The columns show the diagnosed condition, while the rows show the actual conditions. The correct classification rate was highest for the diverted flow (96.08%), while it was lowest for the slugging condition (62%).

The performance of the naive Bayes classifier is only partly accurate for blockage and leakage due to the fact that small valve openings cause only minor changes in the flow regime because of valve non-linearities. The benchmark dataset has shown that the naive Bayes classifier cannot necessarily handle issues such as non-linearity and multi-modality that are typical of real processes.

8.3. Process and alarm data fusion with a two-stage Bayesian classifier

This section demonstrates the application of decision-level fusion to the benchmark dataset [11]. The outputs of monitoring systems for alarm logs and process measurements are fused on the decision-level using a two-stage Bayesian classifier. In the case of alarm and process measurements the fusion is not trivial, as process measurements are numerical and regularly sampled, while alarm logs appear at discrete times. Therefore it is better to perform their fusion at the decision level. Once the binary features are extracted from the alarm logs, as shown in Section 5.2, they can be used as inputs to a classifier. Feature extraction is also applied to the process data. In this case a multivariate PCA approach is used to remove correlation from the sensor measurements.

For both alarm and process data a naive Bayes classifier is used to calculate individual class probabilities, then the monitoring results are fused on the decision-level in a Bayesian way calculating the final class probability. The training, validation and testing of the algorithm were conducted using a rule-of thumb 60–20–20% split [34] of the dataset for operating conditions A and B separately. Furthermore, the diagnosis accuracies of the trained model has been checked on the test set and the results were comparable to the results achieved using the training and validation set, hence the trained model was not overfitted.

The final results are shown in Table 10 both for the cases where the alarm logs and process measurements are considered inde-

pendently and for the case where the two data sources are fused. Fusing both process and alarm data together on the decision-level improved the performance of the algorithm. These results showed that even in the case of only a few alarm events occurring as shown in Fig. 5, the decision-level fusion of process and alarm data was able to improve the performance of the fault diagnosis relative to the case of only considering process data. The result shows that the alarm logs and process measurements in the benchmark dataset contain complementary information, which can be exploited with decision-level fusion methods.

9. Summary of challenges and directions of future work

The PRONTO benchmark dataset presents the complexities of real data from an industrial-scale process facility. It includes process measurements, alarm logs, high-frequency flow and pressure measurements, as well as videos and operation logs.

This dataset can support researchers in developing and validating fault detection and diagnosis algorithms using heterogeneous data, as shown in Section 8. It also has potential uses in demonstrating on-line implementation, as will be discussed in Section 9.2 below. The benchmark dataset also can have value as a teaching resource, by providing real data from an industrial-scale facility. Section 9.3 will briefly touch upon this topic.

9.1. Fault detection and diagnosis algorithms using heterogeneous data

This section itemises the issues inherent in handling heterogeneous data for the purposes of fault detection and diagnosis.

- *Pre-processing.* Heterogeneous datasets require extra pre-processing efforts due to the disparate data sources. For example, the high-frequency measurements and process measurements in this dataset need to be synchronised and their formats need to be unified.
- *Signal processing, feature extraction, feature selection.* The PRONTO benchmark dataset offers the opportunity to test, validate and develop methods for efficient signal processing of the high frequency data. Feature extraction and feature selection methods may be developed using any or all data sources available. The large number of sensors included in the experimental set-up provides an interesting challenge for researchers to attempt to determine which sensors and sensor locations are the best suited for monitoring different faults and flow regimes.
- *Data complexity.* The process data show clear multi-modal, non-linear, dynamic, and time-varying behaviours. Therefore FDD algorithms developed for such behaviours can be validated using this dataset.
- *Fault severity detection.* As the faults were induced in a gradual manner, fault evolution monitoring and fault severity detection methods may be tested.
- *Data fusion.* Feature design and FDD methods should be developed for heterogeneous data considering feature- or decision-level fusion in a way that the framework stays modular, robust and is able to leverage the strengths and mitigate the weaknesses of each data source. Data fusion methods are challenged to tackle the problem of heterogeneous data, where each information source provides complimentary information about the system.

Researchers can use the benchmark dataset for development and validation of all the above aspects of FDD algorithms. Moreover, the dataset could inspire ideas for new approaches that take into account important aspects of real industrial data.

9.2. Towards on-line fault detection and diagnosis

This section discusses the challenges in design and implementation of on-line monitoring systems for FDD and suggests how the benchmark dataset can support the research in on-line FDD. The PRONTO heterogeneous benchmark dataset can be used to test the solutions to the following challenges that may exist in on-line implementation:

- *Data acquisition and storage.* Each measurement in a heterogeneous dataset has its own sampling rate and storage policy. Moreover, they are acquired by various systems, and stored in different places. Real-time FDD algorithm using heterogeneous data require communication with different data acquisition systems. Dynamic methods, time and frequency domain methods, and data fusion will also require the storage of historical data.
- *Changes in the sensor network.* The availability of measurements may be affected by scheduled shut-downs and maintenance of the equipment, sensor failures, and the installation of new sensors, any of which may cause the monitoring framework to fail. When using this dataset, these changes can be simulated by adjusting the input measurements sent to the monitoring system. The reliability and flexibility of monitoring systems will benefit from the robust design which can account for irregularities in the measurement.
- *Adaptation.* On-line monitoring systems need to adapt to changes in the process. For instance, the process may move to a new operating condition that is not yet observed in the historical data. The monitoring system needs to adapt to the changes by incorporating the new data in order to improve the on-line monitoring performance and enhance the decision support. This dataset can test the adaptation ability of on-line monitoring systems because it has multiple scenarios for normal and faulty operation. Data from selected scenarios can be excluded during training on the monitoring system in order to provide an unseen scenario for testing.

9.3. A heterogeneous dataset for teaching and learning

The PRONTO benchmark dataset can have value as a teaching resource, by providing real data from an industrial-scale facility to illustrate the application of text book methods for pre-processing, feature design, FDD and data fusion methods. For instance, application of the discrete Fourier transform to the high frequency pressure measurements and to the 1Hz process measurements can illustrate the concept of the Nyquist frequency, and also the relationship between frequency resolution and the duration of the recording of the measurements.

10. Conclusion

This paper has described the PRONTO benchmark dataset. This is a unique resource with a large amount of heterogeneous data from an industrial-scale multiphase flow facility operating under both normal and faulty conditions. The dataset has process measurements, alarm, event and change logs, recordings of measurements from special instruments with fast sampling rates, as well as videos and an operation log. The paper discussed a framework for fault detection and diagnosis. It demonstrated uses for the heterogeneous data types within the dataset both for fault detection and diagnosis, and for feature- and decision-level data fusion. The benchmark dataset is available on-line so that other researchers can use it for development and validation of their own fault detection and diagnosis algorithms. The paper has shown the dataset can be a valuable resource for researchers in the area of fault detection

and diagnosis. The authors believe the PRONTO benchmark dataset will inspire ideas for new approaches that are applicable to real industrial data.

Conflicts of interest

None.

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